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Smart Urbanism Through Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Megaprojects: The Case of China's Healthcare Services

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ABSTRACT

Urban Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies are increasingly being piloted in cities worldwide, constituting a critical element in the evolution of contemporary and future smart cities. Although there is a growing body of research on the integration of AI into healthcare and smart city systems, the specific intersection of urban AI and healthcare in the context of state-led megaprojects remains insufficiently examined, particularly through empirical case studies grounded in local socio-political dynamics. This paper investigates how urban AI impacts healthcare services in a mega-hospital, addressing this significant gap in the literature. The study's contribution is threefold. First, it synthesizes the developmental trajectory of smart healthcare in China, highlighting the integration of AI technologies into the healthcare sector. Second, through an in-depth case study of the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital, it examines three distinct facets of smart applications within the hospital—focusing on patients, medical staff, and hospital administration—to elucidate the characteristics and dynamics of AI megaprojects in healthcare. Third, it delves into the main challenges and advantages of these AI-driven megaprojects in healthcare management and administration, and proposes policy recommendations based on the case study and identified issues and benefits. The findings reveal that while the integration of AI enhances operational efficiency and patient care outcomes, it also introduces challenges related to data privacy, ethical considerations, and infrastructural demands. The study underscores the necessity for integrated strategies that balance technological advancement with public welfare and urban sustainability. By illuminating the complex interplay between technological innovation, healthcare administration, and urban governance, this paper offers valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and healthcare administrators aiming to foster sustainable smart city development.

1 | Introduction

In recent decades, numerous cities have developed and implemented policies and programmes to become smart. The idea of the smart city, while influential in both academic and policy circles, remains conceptually fluid and geographically variable (Hollands 2020; Karvonen et al. 2018). In broad terms, smart cities are understood as urban environments that integrate

information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance service delivery and urban efficiency (Gracias et al. 2023). A smart city is primarily defined as an urban area that integrates information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance the quality and performance of urban services such as energy, transportation, and utilities. In this context, the official aim is to improve efficiency, reduce resource consumption, and engage more effectively and actively with its citizens (Gracias

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et al. 2023). Caragliu et al. (2011) note that the integration of ICT aims to create more efficient urban services and infrastructure, facilitating easier daily activities and work processes for residents. Meanwhile, some scholars also assert that it fundamentally revolves around the application of advanced technologies to enhance the quality of life for its citizens, albeit often in an uneven manner (Batty 2018; Cugurullo 2021; Hollands 2020; Geoghegan and Cugurullo 2025). Recently, artificial intelligence (AI) has been incorporated into the research and practice of smart cities, and several researchers have noted that AI is becoming an increasingly significant component of smart city projects, in the shape of urban AI (Cugurullo 2020; Ingwersen and Serrano-López 2018; Kassens-Noor and Hintze 2020; Yigitcanlar et al. 2024). The concept of ‘urban artificial intelligence’ denotes city-embedded, autonomous learning and decision-making systems Cugurullo (2020). There is now a growing awareness that the development and management of cities is intrinsically connected to the development and management of urban AI (Caprotti et al. 2024; Cugurullo et al. 2023; Palmini and Cugurullo 2023; Xu et al. 2024). AI is an interdisciplinary field that researches and develops theories, methods, technologies, and application systems for simulating, extending and expanding human intelligence (Wisskirchen et al. 2017). According to Yigitcanlar et al. (2020), the future technological infrastructure and management of a smart city will be essentially based on AI-enabled innovations.

Contemporary scholarship recognizes AI as a pivotal force the evolution of smart cities, with an emphasis on its transformative potential for urban infrastructures (Allam and Dhunny 2019; Cugurullo 2021). The influence of AI on urban dynamics is well-documented, particularly in terms of enhancing cities’ functionalities and operational efficiencies (Allam and Dhunny 2019; Batty 2018; Macrorie et al. 2019; Vinuesa et al. 2020). Notably, ‘city brains’—AI-driven digital platforms—are increasingly adopted for real-time urban traffic management (Caprotti and Liu 2022). More recently, the COVID-19 pandemic further underscored the versatility of urban AI through the deployment of robotics for sanitation and logistical support in metropolitan areas, particularly in China (B. Chen et al. 2020). Trencher (2019) extends the scope of urban AI’s benefits to healthcare, public safety, and domestic assistance. It is worth noting that some pandemic responses had to balance such tech-driven measures with privacy protections, exemplified by Moscow’s hybrid model to fight COVID-19 (Revyakin 2022).

While there has been significant research on the integration of AI into both urban infrastructures and healthcare systems, the intersection of urban AI and healthcare in the context of state-led megaprojects has received comparatively less empirical and contextualized attention. Existing literature often addresses AI applications in healthcare or smart city initiatives separately (Hamet and Tremblay 2017; Shah and Chircu 2018). While substantial research has been conducted on AI’s role in enhancing medical diagnostics and patient care (Esteva et al. 2019; Topol 2019) and on smart city developments focusing on transportation, energy management, and urban governance (Albino et al. 2015; Anthopoulos et al. 2019), fewer studies explore how AI-enabled megaprojects—particularly in the Global South—are operationalized in healthcare contexts

and embedded within the socio-political frameworks of urban development. This paper addresses that gap by focusing on how AI technologies are deployed in a Chinese mega-hospital project as part of broader smart urban transformation.

Megaprojects, characterized by their large scale, high cost, and transformative potential, have the capacity to significantly impact urban landscapes and service delivery (Flyvbjerg and Turner 2018). In the context of smart cities, these projects can serve as platforms for integrating advanced AI technologies into urban healthcare systems, potentially revolutionizing service accessibility and efficiency, in a way that alters citizens’ experience (Cugurullo 2020; Cuppini et al. 2025; Yigitcanlar and Cugurullo 2020). However, empirical studies examining this intersection are scarce, leaving a critical gap in both urban studies and healthcare literature (Dwivedi et al. 2019; Macrorie et al. 2019). Furthermore, the integration of AI into urban healthcare megaprojects raises complex issues related to data privacy, ethical considerations, and the so-called *digital divide* (Kitchin 2016; Luque-Ayala and Marvin 2015). For instance, while AI can enhance healthcare efficiency and effectiveness, it necessitates the collection and analysis of vast amounts of personal health data, thereby posing significant privacy concerns (Van Kleek et al. 2018). Additionally, there is a risk that such technologies could exacerbate existing inequalities if they are not implemented with access and inclusivity in mind (Calzada and Cobo 2015; Crawford and Calo 2016).

To better contextualize the contemporary technological transformations of the healthcare sector, it is essential to place them within the broader global landscape of AI integration in healthcare, with particular emphasis on China’s distinct position. The development and deployment of urban AI in Chinese healthcare systems align with global advancements aimed at enhancing diagnostic accuracy, improving patient outcomes, and reducing healthcare costs (Moulaei et al. 2024). However, China’s centralized governance structure, reflecting a developmental state tradition, presents specific challenges and opportunities (Elliott et al. 2024). While China benefits from its rapid technology adoption and vast data availability, it must also navigate significant policy dilemmas related to data privacy, ethical AI use, and the digital divide, which can exacerbate disparities in access to AI-driven healthcare (Y. Chen et al. 2014; Wu et al. 2022). These policy issues are particularly relevant in urban environments like Guangzhou, where investments in smart city infrastructure, including AI-powered healthcare, are advancing rapidly. The integration of AI into the urban healthcare landscape, while promising, raises questions about governance, equity, and the regulation of AI in highly populated urban areas (Moulaei et al. 2024). Thus the technological transformations of the healthcare sector not only reflect local ambitions but also engage with global discourses on AI in healthcare, illustrating both the benefits and challenges of such technologies in complex, urbanized contexts like Guangzhou.

Therefore, the primary purpose of this study is to investigate the Chinese experience of integrating AI into urban healthcare megaprojects, with the broader aim of enriching current understandings of smart city development through the lens of AI-driven healthcare transformation. Rather than assuming the presence of a universal model of AI-related urban and

infrastructural development, this study foregrounds the socio-political and infrastructural specificities of China's AI deployment in healthcare. By examining how AI-enabled megaprojects are transforming the healthcare domain within China's smart cities, this research seeks to shed light on the unique dynamics, governance structures, and implementation challenges specific to the Chinese context. This also contributes to the growing body of work exploring AI's role in smart healthcare services and related environments and infrastructures (Kamruzzaman 2021; Rathi et al. 2021). This exploration not only provides insights into recent technological and infrastructural advancements, but also delves into the policy, ethical, and social dimensions that go hand in hand with such large-scale implementations. By empirically examining health-related megaprojects within the urban context of Guangzhou, China, our research specifically aims to explore the multifaceted effects of AI on key healthcare stakeholders, including patients, healthcare professionals, and management teams.

Guangzhou—a major city within the Greater Bay Area and a national pilot zone for AI innovation—serves as a compelling case study for understanding how urban AI megaprojects unfold in practice. The paper examines the development status, features and attributes of novel applications of smart healthcare services in an existing AI-megaproject. Our findings are used to distinguish AI-enabled smart healthcare from earlier ICT-based approaches, such as those built on the Internet of Things (IoT), highlighting the functional, institutional, and experiential shifts AI brings about in service provision (Cugurullo et al. 2024; Kassens-Noor et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2024). More specifically, this paper addresses the following refined and interconnected research questions:

1. How are AI-based megaprojects conceptualized and implemented in urban healthcare systems?
2. What are the observed impacts—both intended and unintended—of AI-enabled healthcare services on key stakeholders within the context of a Chinese urban megaproject?

Structurally, the paper is divided into three parts. First, the following background section provides an overview of megaprojects in China and reviews the development history of China's smart healthcare. The second part analyses the case of a specific AI-megaproject (Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital) in China to show the urban AI applications in the field of healthcare services within the mega-hospital in the city. Our study identifies the new characteristics of an AI megaproject, compared to traditional smart tech based on the Internet of Things. The final part of the paper summarizes and discusses the impact of an AI-megaproject on healthcare and medical services.

2 | Background

As we mentioned above, the intersection of technological innovation, healthcare administration, and urban governance has become a focal point of contemporary urban geography, particularly within the context of smart city initiatives aimed at

enhancing operational efficiency and quality of life. Scholars posit that the integration of advanced technologies into urban infrastructure can lead to significant improvements in public service delivery and governance (Batty 2018; C. Li et al. 2023) emphasizes that IoT can reduce operational costs and improve efficiency by providing real-time data which can lead to optimized resource allocation and proactive maintenance strategies. Smart cities leverage Internet of Things (IoT) devices, big data analytics, and AI to create interconnected and responsive urban environments. These technologies facilitate real-time data collection and analysis, enabling more informed decision-making processes in healthcare administration and urban management (Kitchin et al. 2017). Despite the evident benefits, the integration of advanced technologies in urban infrastructure is not without challenges. Issues such as data privacy, cybersecurity, and the digital divide must be addressed to ensure equitable and secure implementations (Cugurullo 2018). Additionally, the financial and institutional capacities of cities vary, necessitating tailored approaches that consider local contexts and capabilities (Karvonen et al. 2018).

The growing ubiquity of AI, in particular, is revolutionizing the landscape of urban governance and healthcare administration. AI algorithms are now increasingly employed to process vast amounts of data generated by IoT devices, providing predictive analytics and actionable insights that were previously unattainable (Xu et al. 2024). Scholars argue that AI urbanism marks a shift from traditional smart urbanism, with AI technologies such as autonomous vehicles, robots, and city brains reshaping urban life, governance, and planning (Cugurullo et al. 2023). In the healthcare sector, AI urbanism introduces sophisticated tools for managing public health, including real-time monitoring systems and predictive analytics. These AI systems enhance the capacity of urban health services by providing more accurate diagnostics, personalized treatment plans, and efficient management of health resources (Guo and Cugurullo 2023). AI-driven city brains, for instance, can integrate data from various sources to predict health trends and manage health services more effectively, contributing to improved public health outcomes. The deployment of AI in healthcare administration involves the use of machine learning algorithms, natural language processing, and predictive analytics to process vast amounts of health data generated by IoT devices and electronic health records (EHRs) (Jiang et al. 2017). These technologies enable real-time monitoring and analysis, facilitating more informed decision-making processes and optimizing resource allocation within healthcare systems. The integration of AI in healthcare administration also addresses operational inefficiencies by automating routine administrative tasks such as appointment scheduling, billing, and inventory management. This form of automation not only reduces administrative costs but also allows healthcare professionals to devote more time to direct patient care, thereby improving the overall efficiency of healthcare services (Davenport and Kalakota 2019). Furthermore, AI facilitates the creation of interconnected health systems within smart cities, where data from various sources, including hospitals, clinics, and wearable devices, can be seamlessly integrated and analyzed to provide a comprehensive view of public health trends and individual patient health records (Raghupathi and Raghupathi 2014).

Moreover, AI-driven systems can enhance the transparency and accountability of healthcare governance. By leveraging blockchain technology, for instance, AI can ensure secure and transparent management of health records, reducing the risk of data breaches and ensuring the integrity of health information (Tagde et al. 2021). This dynamic can foster greater trust between citizens and urban health authorities, as individuals are assured of the confidentiality and accuracy of their health data. Additionally, AI can streamline administrative processes such as patient registration, billing, and appointment scheduling, reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies and improving the overall patient experience (Davenport and Kalakota 2019). The implementation of AI in urban healthcare governance also supports the development of more inclusive and participatory governance models. AI-powered platforms can analyze public feedback and social media data to gauge citizen sentiments and identify community health needs, enabling urban authorities to tailor health services to the diverse needs of the population (Nam and Pardo 2011). This inclusivity is further enhanced by digital health platforms that facilitate direct communication between citizens and healthcare providers, allowing for more responsive and personalized care. Overall, AI has emerged as a pivotal force, reshaping public administration by enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and responsiveness in urban health services (Agarwal et al. 2015; Anthopoulos et al. 2016; Pencheva et al. 2018; T. Q. Sun and Medaglia 2019).

2.1 | Megaprojects in China

In the age of planetary urbanization, most megaprojects have become urban in nature and location (Dogan and Stupar 2017). Megaprojects are usually defined as major investment commitments with vast complexity and long-lasting impacts on cities and public administration (Altshuler and Luberoff 2004; Flyvbjerg and Turner 2018). Research has noted that megaprojects are considered large-scale single or multi-purpose capital investments (Van Marrewijk et al. 2008). According to Yuan et al. (2021, 1), ‘the initiation and development of megaprojects can significantly contribute to economic, social, and cultural advancement.’

With the rapid growth of urbanization, numerous urban and infrastructure megaprojects have grown exponentially in size and scope over the last 2 decades, particularly in developing countries (Flyvbjerg et al. 2003; Hu et al. 2016). Since the Reform and Opening Up¹ in China, over half of China’s population now lives in cities, and more than 100 Chinese cities have populations exceeding one million (Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development 2020). In 2021, all levels of government provided special bonds for large infrastructure projects, in order to achieve the annual objective of economic development and expand domestic demand (s. Sun and Wang 2021).

As of this writing, in Guangzhou, for example, the capital of the Guangdong Province in southern China and a first-tier city, the local government intends to invest hugely in megaprojects through urban transformations (Guangzhou Development and Reform Commission 2022). According to the ‘2022 Guangzhou Key Project Planning’ from the Guangzhou Development and

Reform Commission, Guangzhou will develop 650 megaprojects with an annual planned investment of 345.2 billion yuan (equal to 50 billion EUR or 54 billion USD). These megaprojects will feature AI technology and several of them will focus on healthcare (Guangzhou Development and Reform Commission 2022).

2.2 | Healthcare in China

As mentioned above, AI has impacted many cities, and it is significantly transforming their healthcare sector. In October 2016, the 2030 Health China Planning Outline released by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China stated that (Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party and State Council of the People’s Republic of China 2017, 12)

‘The goal is to raise the overall health level of Chinese people. The Chinese medical industry must transition from offering ‘healthcare’ to providing ‘health services’ and move towards future smart healthcare.’

The Chinese government is facing many healthcare challenges, such as insufficient and unevenly distributed medical resources (Lv et al. 2019), internal brain drains (Zweig 2006), and medical inequity (Wang et al. 2019). These challenges have resulted in increased demand for smart healthcare. Simultaneously, China’s large population base and market for AI applications provide an excellent foundation for developing smart healthcare and smart hospitals. Therefore, with the support of national policy, the market, and technology, the Chinese healthcare sector has seized opportunities for AI development since 2016 (Wei 2018).

With the advancement of AI technologies and the growing demand for healthcare in China, since 2015 the central and local governments have issued a series of policies focused on smart healthcare (Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party and State Council of the People’s Republic of China 2017; General Office of the State Council 2018; National Health Commission 2017). Nowadays, in China, all levels of government and the public pay close attention to the development of smart healthcare because of the following reasons. First, the government aims to optimize the medical experience and service efficiency by accelerating the construction of smart medical information systems (National Health Commission 2020). Second, under the effect of policy guidance and technological progress, Chinese healthcare providers are accelerating the development of smart hospitals. Third, the development of smart hospitals promotes the efficient allocation of healthcare resources and provides a wide range of quality healthcare services to China’s central and western regions. Owing to historical reasons, the provision of medical services was relatively scarce in these regions (National Health Commission 2017).

In recent years, the Chinese government has selected Guangzhou to promote smart healthcare and AI development. In 2018, a research group from Guangzhou Medical University trained a deep-learning system on 101 million data points generated from the electronic records of 1.3 million patient visits to a medical

center in Guangzhou (Liang et al. 2019). China's first smart hospital featuring AI was opened in Guangzhou in 2019. Today the AI system can provide recommendations to patients before they arrive at the hospital and help them make appointments and payments through the mobile payment account of Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital. A smart diagnosis system also helps doctors prescribe medications. In addition to paying bills online, patients can establish their medical profile through a facial recognition software on their smartphones (Wenfang 2018). These AI applications will be discussed in more detail in the remainder of the paper.

3 | Methods

Guangzhou's new hospital megaproject provides a useful case study of how healthcare issues are being addressed through urban AI, for several reasons. Firstly, the Guangzhou government is actively promoting AI-enabled healthcare services through a mega-hospital, showcasing the city's innovative approach to healthcare technology. In 2014, the hospital became the first Internet Hospital in China, thereby providing high-quality medical services for more patients in less developed areas of Guangdong Province, where medical resources are scarce (Guangdong second provincial general hospital 2022). In 2019, the hospital first broadcasted a surgery to another hospital 200 km away with the assistance of 5G + 4 K technologies (G. Li et al. 2021). Furthermore, in 2021, the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital and Huawei Technologies jointly held a conference to announce the upgrading of the hospital to an AI-enabled hospital. To build a database, the hospital spent nearly two years studying more than 100,000 of its digital medical records and over 300 million medical records dating back to the 1990s from other hospitals in China. According to the director of the hospital, Tian Junzhang, the hospital's AI system has an accuracy rate of over 90% for diagnosing more than 200 diseases (E. Huang 2018).

This type of initiative aligns with the concept of an influential case, as defined by Seawright and Gerring (2008), because it can significantly impact policy and practice in similar urban contexts. The city's approach to integrating AI in healthcare can provide valuable insights into the broader adoption and challenges of such technologies in other high-density, innovation-oriented East Asian metropolises including Hong Kong, Seoul, and Tokyo. Secondly, Guangzhou is a large central city with a

population exceeding 13 million, and it serves as the core of the Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macau Greater Bay Area. As one of China's designated national central cities and a key hub in regional AI experimentation, Guangzhou features a complex healthcare infrastructure, a rapidly digitizing public sector, and a demographically diverse urban population. According to Yin (2014), selecting a typical or representative case can help in understanding broader trends and generalizing findings to similar contexts. In this context, Guangzhou's demographic significance refers to its scale, urban density, and the diversity of its population in terms of age, income, and digital literacy, while its geographic significance lies in its strategic location within a national policy corridor promoting AI innovation. These characteristics make Guangzhou not only a valuable case for understanding urban AI implementation in China, but also a window into how urban megaprojects intersect with healthcare transformation in rapidly modernizing cities.

The empirical findings presented in this paper emanate from qualitative data meticulously gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data collection spanned from 2021 to 2022 and was executed through participant observation and anonymous in-depth semi-structured interviews involving eight participants. The choice of qualitative methods is justified by the exploratory nature of this study and the complexity of the phenomena under investigation. Qualitative research allows for an in-depth understanding of the contextual factors and stakeholder experiences associated with AI-enabled healthcare within smart city megaprojects (Creswell and Clark 2017). In this context, semi-structured interviews provide flexibility to explore participants' perspectives while ensuring that the discussion remains aligned with the research objectives.

Participants included policymakers from the local government, as well as doctors and researchers affiliated with pertinent research institutes located in Guangzhou. For further clarity, Table 1 provides detailed information on the interviewees, and Table 2 outlines the guiding questions used in the interviews (sample), offering transparency in the methodology employed. While the core guiding questions (outlined in Table 2) were consistent across interviews, they were adapted to suit each interviewee's expertise, in line with the philosophy of semi-structured interviews. For example, the questions asked to the policymaker from the local government focused more on issues of policy implementation and governance aspects related to urban healthcare.

TABLE 1 | List of the interviewees.

Interviewees (no.)	Occupation and expertise	City	Date
Interviewee 1	Doctor from local hospital	Guangzhou	March 2021
Interviewee 2	Doctor from local hospital	Guangzhou	March 2021
Interviewee 3	Doctor from local hospital	Guangzhou	May 2021
Interviewee 4	Nurse from local hospital	Guangzhou	May 2021
Interviewee 5	Nurse from local hospital	Guangzhou	Sep 2021
Interviewee 6	IT support staff from hospital	Guangzhou	Sep 2021
Interviewee 7	IT staff from AI company	Guangzhou	Sep 2021
Interviewee 8	Administrator from the hospital	Guangzhou	March 2022

TABLE 2 | Guiding questions for semi-structured interviews (Sample).

1. How has the implementation of AI systems affected your workload and efficiency in daily tasks in your hospital?
2. How has AI-assisted documentation and data entry systems influenced your workflow and productivity?
3. In what ways has AI-enabled data collection supported your decision-making and policy development processes?
4. What benefits have you observed for patients, such as reduced waiting times, since introducing AI technologies like the smart dispensary service in your hospital?
5. In what ways has AI contributed to health system reforms and supported your organization's response during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic?
6. What challenges have you faced when integrating AI products with existing hospital systems, especially concerning data sharing between different company platforms?

Secondary data was systematically collated from a variety of scholarly materials. This included academic presentations and peer-reviewed journal articles, which provided a robust theoretical framework and contextual background for the study. Additionally, and most critically, government documents served as a cornerstone of the secondary data (some examples as following). These documents encompassed policy papers, strategic reports, and official publications, offering an authoritative and detailed account of the regulatory and operational landscape pertinent to the study. This dual approach of integrating primary insights with substantiated secondary sources enriches the empirical foundation of the research, ensuring a holistic and multi-faceted understanding of the subject matter. The comprehensive nature of the data collection process underscores the rigor and depth of the study, which aims to contribute significantly to the academic discourse in the field of geography and beyond.

4 | The 2030 Health China Planning Outline

The 2030 Health China Planning Outline is a national policy developed by the Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party² and the State Council of the People's Republic of China.³ One of its core principles is innovation, and it aims to guide and promote the development of smart healthcare in China.

- The Action Plan for the Development of 'Internet + Health' in Guangdong Province

The Action Plan is a regional policy developed by the People's Government of Guangdong Province. This document provides policy support for developing smart health services in Guangdong province.

- The Opinions on Promoting the Application of Healthcare Big Data

The Opinions are a set of local policies developed by the People's Government of Guangzhou Municipality. According to this document, the Guangzhou municipality is seeking to accelerate the development of artificial intelligence for healthcare.

5 | Findings

The hospital's healthcare system is underpinned by a comprehensive array of existing IT environments and frameworks that are instrumental in facilitating the delivery of medical services. Currently, systems such as Electronic Health Records (EHR) are extensively utilized to manage patient data and streamline clinical workflows, thereby providing a foundational infrastructure for the integration of AI (Moulai et al. 2024; Topol 2019). EHR systems enable the consolidation of patient information, which is critical for data-driven AI applications aiming to enhance diagnostic accuracy and personalize treatment plans. However, despite the widespread implementation of EHR, significant gaps remain in adopting more advanced frameworks, such as cloud-based AI diagnostics and decision-support tools. The integration of AI technologies into hospital IT systems holds the potential to improve diagnostic precision, reduce human error, and optimize treatment recommendations (Esteva et al. 2019). Meanwhile, the adoption of AI systems is influenced by the spatial distribution of healthcare resources, population density, and the unique healthcare demands of urban populations (Graham and Marvin 2002). Drawing on our empirical findings, we will see how Guangzhou's Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital has successfully integrated advanced urban AI technologies into its original IT system, shedding light on how these innovations enhance patient care, diagnostics, and overall hospital operations.

This section examines the characteristics of an ongoing AI megaproject, specifically the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital, and how urban AI is utilized within this large-scale endeavor to tackle particular healthcare challenges. Scholars have emphasized that smart cities fundamentally center on deploying advanced technologies to improve the quality of life for citizens (Batty 2018; Hollands 2020). Consequently, this section concentrates on how smart technologies assist stakeholders in the hospital setting. It is structured into three parts, each addressing a distinct dimension of smart application in the hospital: patients, doctors, and hospital management.

5.1 | Smart Technologies for Patients

The Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital integrates the online and offline medical treatment processes through urban artificial intelligence. Through AI-enabled healthcare, the hospital lowers the threshold for access to smart healthcare services. In the past, patients needed several apps to finish the medical treatment process by themselves. Compared to the traditional internet health hospital, all the smart services for patients now run automatically due to the integration of AI solutions. Before going to the hospital, patients talk on WeChat⁴

with virtual assistants powered by AI to identify the appropriate department for their issues and then schedule appointments with a doctor (Figure 1). When the patients walk into the AI-enabled hospital on the appointment day, the hospital sends navigation instructions and waiting time messages to patients automatically through WeChat. At the end of the visit, the smart system automatically sends the payment link, prescriptions and medication advice to patients. Patients can also access their health records, medication lists, and treatment plans by using WeChat. In essence, most of the communication taking place in the hospital is now mediated by AI (Figure 2).

FIGURE 1 | Dialog Box with a virtual assistant on WeChat. After processing the information about a patient's symptoms, the virtual assistant transfers that person to another channel to talk with a real doctor or it helps patients to make an appointment. (Source: authors' original.) [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 2 | Via WeChat, patients can also pay bills, make an appointment, and check personal medical data. (Source: authors' original.) [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

It is worth mentioning the indoor navigation service provided by the hospital. Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital is a large hospital with seven buildings and 79 different departments, covering an area of 150,000 square meters. Patients can easily lose their way within the hospital. However, this issue has been addressed by means of AI. When patients walk into the hospital and click the indoor navigation service button on WeChat, the system can automatically check the appointment details and guide them directly and precisely to the right department (Figure 3).

When we talk about smart services based on smartphones, it is important to acknowledge that this can be difficult for some groups of citizens due to the digital divide. In order to address this issue, the hospital now features some robots in the reception, which are officially called 'Guide Robots (Figure 4).' These robots provide a service that is akin to the smartphone-based

FIGURE 3 | Indoor navigation service within WeChat, that automatically enables path planning. (Source: authors' original.) [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 4 | A guide robot operating in the hospital reception. (Source: authors' original.) [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

navigational service described above. In this context, the main function of the robot is to show the path planning to the patients. Meanwhile, robots can also lead patients directly to a department if it is located on the same floor. Furthermore, the robot can help patients register with the right doctor or department according to the patients' symptoms. The guide robot is connected to the hospital's AI platform, so patients can also talk with it to obtain information. For example, patients can directly ask a robot about the working hours of the various departments, information about tests and examinations, the medical service fees and reimbursement rates. Urban AI is a system that can train itself by collecting and analyzing large quantities of data (Cugurullo 2020). Therefore, with more and more conversations between patients and guide robots, the robots' answers are expected to become more comprehensive and accurate.

In addition, regarding the digital divide between rural and urban areas in China, the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital provides smart healthcare services in 2200 villages in Guangdong Province. Furthermore, the hospital is expanding its services to other provinces through an online medical alliance mode, including Linzhi in Tibet and Fuquan in Guizhou. When patients visit village clinics, doctors can check their previous medical data from the hospital's central database. If village doctors face intractable diseases, they can transmit patient files, such as electrocardiograms and blood sugar data, to the hospital instantaneously for remote diagnosis by doctors from Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital. One interviewee (Interview 1), a local doctor, described this process, explaining that:

'Recently a patient who lives far away from Guangzhou, such as Qingyuan,⁵ felt chest pain and tightness and came to the local health station to see a doctor. The local doctor instructed him to put on the remote diagnosis and treatment equipment. A few minutes later, I can see his ECG images on my ECG screen in the hospital.'

5.2 | Smart Technologies for Healthcare Workers

The hospital alleviates the workloads of doctors and nurses by implementing a smart ward equipped with real-time information and proactive management capabilities. There is a bedside digital display in the smart ward, and patients can view the examination/surgery appointment situation, examination reports, and hospital bills by themselves instead of contacting a nurse. At the nurse station, twin electronic screens display the real-time data of each patient, as well as any medical advice, examination reports, and all vital signs. Consequently, the nurse on duty can easily monitor patients remotely while issuing orders and alert other staff members via two large screens. This reduces the workload of medical staff, who no longer have to visit multiple wards to check each patient's stability or switch between multiple systems to query doctors' notes and check reports. As the quotes below

show, most interviewees felt that AI technology reduced their workload:

'Yes, I can receive and send the message by clicking the screen in the nurse station' (Interviewee 4)

'Yes, I think the new AI system reduced our workload' (Interviewee 2).

'Before, I needed to spend a lot of time on ward inspection to discover the changes of the disease of the patient. But now, I can get the real-time data of each patient even when I sit in the office' (Interviewee 3).

Furthermore, the hospital introduced a smart dispensary service. In China, patients need to bring the prescription to the dispensary within the hospital to get their medications. Therefore, many staff members used to work in the dispensary to fill in the prescriptions. The downsides were that preparing the prescriptions was time-consuming and thus the waiting time for patients was long. After introducing the smart dispensary service, this process has become more efficient. First, after a visit, the patients' medical information is transferred to a machine outside the dispensary. Second, patients print a voucher for picking up the medicine by scanning their ID card or medical card. Third, they can find the information about the pickup window on the voucher. In the final step, patients go to the pickup window, scan the barcode on the voucher and pay for the medical costs. The automatic medicine delivery machines receive the patient's information and automatically dispense medications. Before giving a medicine to a patient, a pharmacist at the front desk scans the barcode on the voucher again and checks the patient's prescription information to confirm that every detail is correct, so human agents are still involved in the process. Some of the staff members interviewed at the hospital commented:

'All in all, the operation of the smart dispensary service contributed to a shortened waiting time for patients and reduced work intensity for pharmacists.' (Interviewee 5)

'According to our internal investigation, before the launch of the smart dispensary service, the average waiting time was 15 min for each patient. Now the average waiting time is reduced to 6.6 min.' (Interviewee 4)

Alongside these standard smart technologies used inside the hospital, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) operated by AI are used outside the hospital (Figure 5). During the COVID-19 pandemic, China's government adopted a zero-tolerance approach to combat COVID-19, meaning that the local governments had to carry out mass-scale PCR tests each time an outbreak occurred. For example, from 09/04/2022 to 10/04/2022, the Guangzhou government carried out 19,180,000 PCR tests. In order to facilitate the process, Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital used drones to transport PCR test samples between the hospital and the test center. In terms of

logistics, a drone can fly from the hospital to another test center located 15 km away. The whole process takes about 10 min instead of 30 min by road. According to one interviewee who worked in the IT department of the hospital (Interviewee 6):

‘The UAV can fly at about 50km/h while at 90 m. The UAV can carry 5 kg of goods at one time, which means it can carry more than 200 samples.’

5.3 | Smart Technologies for Management

Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital digitizes the physical world and develops a digitally integrated regulatory and decision-making system, by means of a smart digital brain

enabled by AI. More specifically, the hospital uses cloud computing and AI to create a unified and integrated view of medical operations, administration management, security, and firefighting. The hospital utilizes a highly complex set of networks to support smart management, and the smart brain overviews every aspect of it, thereby developing a holistic perspective.

The following picture shows how a smart brain works in the hospital (Figure 6). A large screen displays a dynamic 3D model of the hospital area. It shows and monitors various information data of the hospital in real-time. Meanwhile, it can also access the real-time situation of different departments of the hospital, enabling intelligent asset management of the hospital area. For instance, the screen shows the number of patients in the outpatient area, the number of people waiting for a consultation, the number of doctors, the status of the operating theater,

FIGURE 5 | A UAV leaving the hospital during an outbreak (何雪华 2021). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 6 | An interface of the smart brain in the hospital (罗平章 和 张仕杰 2021). [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

and the operation of the lift. This provides strong technical support for managers' decision-making. The following three examples show how the management department uses the smart brain to improve the management of the hospital in relation to three different aspects.

First, inside the hospital, people can see medical waste collectors pushing a yellow medical waste collection trolley around the various departments to collect medical waste. After collection, the trolley can automatically weigh and check the medical waste, and then the collectors use a handheld machine to generate a QR code that includes different information such as time, location, category, weight and handover person. By attaching a QR code to each medical waste bag, the hospital not only can avoid the hassle of inaccurate data during the process but can also have more detailed information on medical waste generated from each department. All the medical waste data received are uploaded onto the smart brain in real-time. In the management department (monitoring room), hospital managers can see on a digital screen the real-time data of the medical waste. Through the screen, they also can see the collection, storage and handover status of medical waste within the hospital. Furthermore, hospital managers can see the real-time location of the medical waste trolley.

Second, healthcare sector workers are currently a 'high-risk' profession due to tense doctor-patient relations which have often led to incidents (朱力 and 袁迎春 2014). Guangdong second provincial general hospital is addressing this issue via AI. The AI-enabled security system of the hospital combines different functions such as data collection, video recognition, risk warning and emergency alarm. It employs AI to assist security personnel in identifying risky situations and it generates automatic warnings. For instance, if some people were jostling and arguing, AI-equipped cameras would automatically identify these activities. Then the system would transmit an alert signal to the safety department about this abnormal and potentially dangerous behavior, suggesting the security staff go and stop the situation.

Third, emergency services are an important part of the hospital. Normally, patients are transported to the hospital by ambulance. When the ambulances arrive at the hospital, the first-aid personnel transfer the patient to the emergency department. According to Dúason et al. (2021), important medical information can be easily lost during this process, and the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital is actively introducing smart technologies to mitigate this problem. The hospital has established an emergency rescue network among first-aid personnel, ambulances, emergency command centers, and hospitals. When an ambulance receives a patient, it transmits the patient's medical records and tomographic images to the hospital in real-time, allowing first-aid personnel to focus on the patient instead of wasting time handing over documents. Moreover, this allows doctors in the hospital to formulate rescue plans in advance. This AI-managed network of information significantly reduces the time required for patients to reach the hospital for treatment and the risk of losing medical information.

6 | Discussion

An AI-megaproject is the product of urban AI technologies combined with a large-scale urban project, and healthcare is an important dimension of this emerging urban phenomenon, particularly in China. In this context, the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital's integration of urban AI into its operational framework, is an important and useful example of technological innovation in public health administration. The hospital's approach encapsulates an avant-garde model where digital inclusivity and smart healthcare delivery converge to forge a seamless patient experience, a streamlined workflow for healthcare professionals, and an advanced management system. In terms of public administration and development, this example suggests a considerable step forward toward urban resilience and sustainability, particularly from a social point of view given how crucial healthcare is as a social need. Notably, China's recent public sector innovations are increasingly regarded as exemplar in the development literature, in line with the model of healthcare management that our study has examined (Elliott et al. 2024). It underscores a paradigm shift from traditional healthcare systems to a more responsive and adaptive framework that leverages the proficiencies of AI to cater to the dynamic needs of urban populations. The Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital's initiative transcends mere technological innovation, reflecting a deeper commitment to public welfare and equity, whereby urban AI becomes a fulcrum balancing efficiency with accessibility. Such a citizen-centric ethos is reminiscent of how street-level healthcare workers prioritize community needs to create public value during societal crises (Mousa et al. 2025). Moreover, the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital's outreach into rural vicinities illustrates a commendable endeavor to bridge urban-rural divides, effectively decentralizing healthcare services and fostering a more inclusive healthcare network. This is crucial in the context of China's rapid urbanization and related challenges to healthcare accessibility. Indeed, the critical importance of governance capacity for ensuring such equitable access has been highlighted on a global scale; recently, for example, when governance shortcomings led to inequitable COVID-19 vaccine distribution in many places (Bhuiyan 2022). Overall, we have presented urban AI as a beneficial technology, specifically in the field of healthcare. However, there are still substantial gaps and issues to address. As the literature on smart urbanism clearly indicates, smart tech is a double-edged sword, so it is important to stress both its benefits and challenges, which is precisely what this final section attempts to do (Cugurullo 2018; Kitchin 2015).

6.1 | Main Benefits

The primary benefit of an AI-megaproject is reducing the strain on medical human resources. As China's population grows older, with 300 million people suffering from chronic diseases, it seems nearly impossible to keep up with the increasing demand for healthcare (Shilian et al. 2020). According to the latest data from

the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, China has 1.8 practicing doctors per 1000 citizens, compared with 2.6 for the United States and 4.3 for Sweden (Ho 2018). Patients in rural and remote areas can access healthcare services based in urban areas through remote AI platforms. Furthermore, the structure and procedure of healthcare services in hospitals can be optimized by using AI to examine massive datasets.

The second benefit is restructuring the healthcare service model, shifting from ‘treatment’ to ‘prevention’ and from passive consultation within the hospital to health services available at any time and in any location. As the following interview quote illustrates, some interviewees believe that AI can swiftly and effectively integrate medical data, allowing every patient to have electronic health records and creating vast health datasets:

‘I don’t need to type words using Chinese characters one by one anymore, I just need to type a few words, and the system gives me the suggestion and automatically fills in the rest’ (Interviewee 2).

Healthcare institutions and their staff can proactively identify individuals with problematic health conditions by monitoring smart mobile terminals or wearable devices. They can then provide health tips, health improvement skills, and medical measures in advance by analyzing and collating data via smart healthcare applications.

Finally, some interviewees believe that AI-enabled healthcare services will help China develop more scientific health policies. According to Li Lanjuan, an academic at the Chinese Academy of Engineering and vice president of the Chinese Medical Association, AI simulates medical processes, diagnosis, advice, and treatment plans through massive datasets, which will lead to significant changes in the healthcare sector (王圣媛 2017). Overall, our findings, exemplified by the following interview quotes, suggest that in China there is a growing feeling that AI is changing public health policies for the better.

‘Yes, AI helps our health system reform, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.’ (Interviewee 8)

‘My personal feeling is AI is helpful for my work. When I attend a meeting (local People’s Congress or local committee of the Chinese people’s political consultative conference), I use data collected by AI to make policy suggestions.’ (Interviewee 2)

6.2 | Main Challenges

Despite the benefits discussed above, some problems and challenges have yet to be addressed in the areas of medical data, system security, construction guarantees, resource sharing, and evaluation systems.

Currently, the focus of China’s smart healthcare is gradually shifting away from the stage of hospital informatization, which is primarily focused on piecemeal and siloed applications, and

toward a more advanced stage focused on unified and coherent AI-enabled mega-hospitals (宫芳芳 et al. 2013; 游世梅 2015; 陈敏 2018). However, during this process, AI-megaprojects face serious data issues. During the field research, most interviewees pointed out that data issues are the biggest challenge for the combination of urban AI and healthcare services. AI relies on large volumes of data to improve decision-making capabilities (Duan et al. 2019; Dwivedi et al. 2019). However, in China medical data are often not shared between different departments, thereby leading to the so-called ‘data isolated island’ phenomenon (宫芳芳 et al. 2013; 游世梅 2015; 董华 and 刘太强 2014; 项高悦 and 沈永健 2016). One interviewee from a local AI company (Interviewee 7) also shared the following insight:

‘Hospitals need to connect with AI companies when they need to use artificial intelligence products. However, this docking process presents some issues: the hospital system was relatively closed. Different hospital electronic systems were previously developed by different companies, and there are barriers between the companies’ systems. Therefore, it is difficult for an artificial intelligence company to integrate data from different hospitals.’

The lack of uniformity in data types is another key issue. An interviewee (Interviewee 6) provided another example:

‘When we train the models, we usually have a database, and our respective algorithms are trained based on this data. However, every company’s data and models are different.’

According to the interviewee, sharing medical data between different healthcare providers is difficult because of the lack of uniformity in data types. It is difficult to form an effective data sharing and exchange mechanism for three main reasons. First, the status of hospital information development is not uniform across the country. In remote areas and rural hospitals, smart infrastructures are underdeveloped, and the effective data volume is small because there are not many smart technologies that are producing data in the first place. Second, different hospitals use different systems and equipment from different suppliers, so data storage modes and principles differ. Finally, different system interface standards make it difficult to achieve effective data integration between different hospitals.

The collection of extensive patient data using AI technologies presents a double-edged sword. On one hand, as Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier (2013) suggest, big data can lead to ground-breaking developments in healthcare, improving diagnostics and patient care. On the other hand, it raises significant privacy concerns. Patients may not be fully aware of the scope of the data being collected or its future use. This lack of awareness can lead to distrust in the healthcare system and hesitancy to share necessary information, potentially undermining the efficacy of healthcare delivery. For public administration, this presents a policy conundrum, as highlighted by Xiang and Cai (2021), where the benefits of large-scale data collection for public health must be weighed against individual

privacy rights. Effective policies must therefore strike a balance, ensuring that data is used responsibly and ethically while safeguarding individual privacy. Indeed, other cities facing COVID-19 have adopted 'hybrid' solutions to achieve such a balance, as demonstrated by Moscow's approach combining large-scale technology use with strict privacy safeguards (Revyakin 2022). The conundrum for public administration lies in balancing the immense benefits of AI-driven data collection with the imperative to protect individual privacy. Developing effective policies in this context requires a deep understanding of both the technological aspects of AI and the ethical, legal, and social implications of data use. Policies must be designed to ensure that data is used in ways that are ethical, responsible, and aligned with public health goals without infringing on individual privacy rights. This includes implementing stringent data protection measures, ensuring data anonymization where possible, and establishing clear guidelines for data usage, thereby fostering a culture of trust and transparency.

6.3 | Policy Recommendations

Building upon the findings from the integration of AI in smart urbanism within China's healthcare sector, a set of comprehensive policy recommendations is proposed to maximize the benefits of such innovations while addressing the inherent challenges. First and foremost, it is imperative for governments to establish a robust and standardized framework for data management that ensures seamless interoperability across different systems and institutions. This framework should specifically address the 'data isolated island' phenomenon, which often hampers the effective use of AI technologies in urban settings (宫芳芳 et al. 2013). To achieve this, policymakers must prioritize data security and privacy, aligning with global best practices to foster public trust and ensure compliance with both national and international data protection standards. Such a framework should include protocols for data sharing between public and private entities, encryption methods to protect sensitive information, and clear guidelines on data ownership and access rights.

Another critical policy area is addressing the digital divide, which remains a significant barrier to the equitable deployment of smart urban technologies (Fong 2009). Governments should develop targeted strategies to ensure that rural and underserved urban populations have equal access to AI-enabled healthcare and other smart city services. This could involve expanding broadband infrastructure, subsidizing the acquisition of digital devices, and promoting digital literacy programs tailored to different demographic groups, including the elderly and those with limited prior exposure to technology (McDonough 2016). Furthermore, fostering partnerships between urban and rural healthcare providers can facilitate the diffusion of best practices and technological innovations across different regions, ensuring that advancements in smart healthcare benefit all citizens, regardless of their geographic location.

In parallel, policymakers must give due consideration to the ethical implications of AI deployment in public services, so that

their distribution is even, equal and in line with the needs of multiple stakeholders, particularly citizens (Cugurullo and Xu 2024). Establishing comprehensive ethical guidelines is essential to govern the use of AI, particularly in sensitive sectors like healthcare (Chang 2021). These guidelines should be developed in consultation with a wide range of stakeholders, including ethicists, technologists, healthcare professionals, and representatives from civil society. They should address issues such as informed consent, transparency in AI decision-making processes, the prevention of algorithmic bias, and the safeguarding of individual autonomy. Additionally, the guidelines should ensure that AI technologies are used in ways that enhance public welfare, rather than exacerbating existing inequalities or introducing new forms of harm.

7 | Conclusion

Particularly in healthcare, the integration of AI into smart city initiatives can be a transformative force toward more resilient and sustainable urban ecosystems. The case study of the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital megaproject embodies this transition, where AI-driven solutions have been leveraged to enhance service delivery, patient care, and operational efficiency, ultimately fostering a more inclusive healthcare system. In doing so, this megaproject demonstrably creates public value by improving the services provided to citizens in relation to healthcare (Mousa et al. 2025). AI-megaprojects, as this paper has shown, can significantly alleviate the pressure on healthcare systems, which is particularly crucial in the face of aging populations and the growing prevalence of chronic diseases. The study by Topol (2019) also highlights how AI can augment diagnostic accuracy and streamline administrative processes, thereby reducing the workload on healthcare professionals and allowing them to focus more on patient care. The deployment of such technologies in Guangzhou's healthcare megaproject underscores the potential for AI to optimize healthcare delivery by harnessing vast datasets, thus enabling a shift from reactive treatment to proactive and preventative care. The Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital's initiative to extend healthcare services to rural areas is a significant step toward bridging the urban-rural healthcare divide, an issue that has been widely documented in health equity research. According to (X. Li et al. 2020), decentralized healthcare models are essential in addressing the disparities in health services between urban and rural populations, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions like China. Similarly, Y. Chen et al. (2014) emphasize that integrating rural areas into broader health networks not only improves access to healthcare but also fosters a more inclusive system that benefits the overall population. This approach aligns with the findings of Zheng and Rodriguez-Monroy (2015), who argue that targeted online medical programs are effective in improving healthcare outcomes in rural communities by ensuring that residents receive timely and adequate medical care. Consequently, the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital's online medical efforts can be seen as a practical application of these principles, contributing to the reduction of healthcare inequalities and supporting the goal of equitable health access for all citizens.

The findings of this study demonstrate that integrating AI into healthcare megaprojects in China can enhance the existing healthcare domain of smart cities by advancing diagnostic accuracy, operational efficiency, and patient engagement. Drawing on the case of the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital, it becomes evident that China's centralized approach enables rapid implementation and scalability of AI-driven healthcare solutions, supported by extensive data availability. Comparatively, experiences in countries like the United States and Japan reveal challenges such as interoperability issues and cultural resistance to AI technology (Davenport and Kalakota 2019; Shibata and Wada 2011), while the European context emphasizes strict privacy regulations that can hinder AI deployment in healthcare (Morley et al. 2020). These insights suggest that future conceptualizations and strategies of smart urbanism in the healthcare sector should prioritize holistic AI integrations, equitable access, and robust data governance frameworks to balance innovation with ethical considerations, thereby fostering sustainable and inclusive advancements in global urban healthcare systems (Kostkova et al. 2016; Topol 2019).

The journey toward the sustainability of AI in smart healthcare is indeed fraught with critical challenges. One of the most pressing concerns is data privacy, as the vast amounts of personal health information used by AI systems require stringent safeguards to protect against unauthorized access and breaches. According to Reddy et al. (2019), ensuring the confidentiality and security of health data is paramount, yet remains a complex issue given the varying levels of data protection regulations across different regions. Additionally, the lack of uniform data standards presents another significant obstacle. As noted by Johnson et al. (2016), the diversity in data formats and quality hinders the interoperability of AI systems, making it difficult to integrate and analyze data across different platforms and institutions. Furthermore, the risk of creating 'data isolated islands'—where data is siloed within specific organizations or systems—exacerbates these challenges, as it limits the potential for comprehensive data analysis and collaboration. These challenges must be addressed to realize the full potential of AI in transforming smart healthcare (宫芳芳 et al. 2013; 游世梅 2015; 董华 and 刘太强 2014; 项高悦 and 沈永健 2016). Furthermore, the integration of AI necessitates a delicate balance between technological advancement and the safeguarding of individual privacy rights. Here public administration has a pivotal role to play in navigating these challenges. It must foster a regulatory environment that encourages innovation while ensuring that data management practices are transparent, ethical, and privacy-conscious. Moreover, there is a need for capacity building within public institutions to adapt to the AI-driven paradigm of smart healthcare. This aligns with recent calls to bridge the AI skills gap in government by developing human-centric AI governance competencies among public sector professionals (Trajkovski 2024), ensuring that administrators are well-equipped to implement and oversee these innovations effectively.

In conclusion, our research confirms what current studies on urban AI and smart urbanism are indicating (Barns 2021; Cugurullo et al. 2023, 2024; Marvin et al. 2022; While et al. 2020). AI has become a fundamental component of smart-

city initiatives, which consolidates existing practices of smart urbanism, while also presenting novel functions, applications and capabilities that go beyond traditional smart technologies (Caprotti et al. 2024; Cugurullo et al. 2024). The AI-enabled software agents, robots and autonomous urban platforms discussed in this paper represent a new wave of smart urbanism that will keep gaining traction in contemporary and future cities, thereby impacting their management and public services, such as healthcare. By examining the Chinese experience, this study has addressed existing gaps in the literature regarding the nexus between urban AI, healthcare, and megaprojects. It has provided empirical evidence of how AI-enabled megaprojects are reshaping the healthcare domain within smart cities, offering insights into the transformative potential of AI in enhancing healthcare delivery and operational efficiency. This research has contributed to a deeper understanding of the complexities and implications of integrating AI into urban healthcare systems, thus expanding the concept of smart cities in relation to recent developments in health technologies (Cugurullo 2021; Trencher 2019). Moreover, the findings have highlighted the importance of considering ethical, social, and policy dimensions in the deployment of AI in healthcare megaprojects. Issues such as data privacy, equitable access, and the digital divide emerge as critical areas that require attention to ensure that the benefits of AI are realized without exacerbating existing inequalities (Crawford and Calo 2016; Kitchin 2016; Van Kleek et al. 2018).

However, the findings from the case study of AI-enabled smart healthcare in China's Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital, while illuminating, may not be readily generalizable to other countries or jurisdictions due to the unique sociopolitical, economic, and infrastructural context within which these developments have occurred. China's government, characterized by a centralized authority with significant control over economic planning and urban development, provides a conducive environment for the rapid implementation and scaling of smart urbanism initiatives, including those powered by artificial intelligence (K. Huang et al. 2021; Marvin et al. 2022). This centralization allows for swift policy enactments, coordinated efforts across multiple sectors, and substantial state-led investments in megaprojects, all of which are crucial in the realization of smart urbanism on a scale witnessed in China. However, such conditions are not universally replicable, especially in more decentralized or democratic nations where urban governance is often fragmented, and where the integration of advanced technologies into urban infrastructure might face more significant challenges related to bureaucratic inertia, political resistance, and public scrutiny. Moreover, China's approach to data governance, marked by a relatively lower emphasis on privacy compared to Western standards, facilitates the extensive data collection necessary for the functioning of AI systems (Ekman and de Esperanza Picardo 2020; Atha et al. 2020). In contrast, jurisdictions with stringent data protection laws might encounter substantial barriers to implementing similar systems. Therefore, while the benefits of smart urbanism—such as enhanced efficiency in urban services and improved public health outcomes—demonstrated in the Chinese context are noteworthy, the challenges highlighted, particularly those related to data management and the digital divide, may manifest differently elsewhere, contingent upon local governance structures, regulatory environments, and

societal norms. Consequently, any attempt to generalize the findings from this study to other global contexts must account for these significant geopolitical and cultural variances, suggesting that the efficacy and challenges of smart urbanism are deeply intertwined with the specificities of governance and urban policy frameworks within individual nations.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Practice Impact Statement

The research offers timely insights into how AI megaprojects are reshaping urban healthcare, using the Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital as a case study. It highlights practical benefits such as improved patient experience, reduced staff workload, and smarter hospital management, while also addressing critical challenges including data fragmentation, privacy concerns, and the digital divide. By examining both the opportunities and limitations of AI in healthcare, this research provides actionable guidance for policymakers, urban planners, and healthcare administrators aiming to implement equitable and sustainable smart health systems.

Endnotes

- ¹ Reform and Opening Up is the official translation of the Chinese economic reform that took place in 1978.
- ² The Central Committee of the Communist Party of China is a political body that comprises the top leaders of the Chinese Communist Party.
- ³ The State Council of the People's Republic of China is the chief administrative authority of China.
- ⁴ As of December 2021, WeChat was the most popular mobile app in China with around 1.3 billion monthly active users Tencent (2021). *Tencent Holdings Limited 2021 Annual Report*. <https://static.www.tencent.com/uploads/2022/04/07/7c31a327fb1c068906b70ba7ebede899.PDF>.
- ⁵ Qingyuan is a city 100 km away from Guangzhou

References

- Agarwal, P. K., J. Gurjar, A. K. Agarwal, and R. Birla. 2015. "Application of Artificial Intelligence for Development of Intelligent Transport System in Smart Cities." *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering* 1, no. 1: 20–30.
- Albino, V., U. Berardi, and R. M. Dangelico. 2015. "Smart Cities: Definitions, Dimensions, Performance, and Initiatives." *Journal of Urban Technology* 22, no. 1: 3–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2014.942092>.
- Allam, Z., and Z. A. Dhunny. 2019. "On Big Data, Artificial Intelligence and Smart Cities." *Cities* 89: 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2019.01.032>.
- Altshuler, A. A., and D. E. Luberoff. 2004. *Mega-projects: The Changing Politics of Urban Public Investment*. Brookings Institution Press.

- Anthopoulos, L., M. Janssen, and V. Weerakkody. 2016. "A Unified Smart City Model (USCM) for Smart City Conceptualization and Benchmarking." *International Journal of Electronic Government Research* 12, no. 2: 77–93. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijegr.2016040105>.
- Anthopoulos, L., M. Janssen, and V. Weerakkody. 2019. "A Unified Smart City Model (USCM) for Smart City Conceptualization and Benchmarking." In *Smart Cities and Smart Spaces: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications*, 247–264.
- Atha, K., J. Callahan, J. Chen, et al. 2020. *China's Smart Cities Development*. SOS International LLC.
- Barns, S. 2021. "Out of the Loop? on the Radical and the Routine in Urban Big Data." *Urban Studies* 58, no. 15: 3203–3210. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00420980211014026>.
- Batty, M. 2018. "Artificial Intelligence and Smart Cities." *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science* 45, no. 1: 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808317751169>.
- Bhuiyan, S. 2022. "COVID-19 Vaccine Equity in Doldrums: Good Governance Deficits." *Public Administration and Development* 42, no. 5: 293–304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1999>.
- Calzada, I., and C. Cobo. 2015. "Unplugging: Deconstructing the Smart City." *Journal of Urban Technology* 22, no. 1: 23–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2014.971535>.
- Caprotti, F., F. Cugurullo, M. Cook, et al. 2024. "Why Does Urban Artificial Intelligence (AI) Matter for Urban Studies? Developing Research Directions in Urban AI Research." *Urban Geography* 45, no. 5: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2024.2329401>.
- Caprotti, F., and D. Liu. 2022. "Platform Urbanism and the Chinese Smart City: The Co-production and Territorialisation of Hangzhou City Brain." *Geojournal* 87, no. 3: 1559–1573. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-020-10320-2>.
- Caragliu, A., C. Del Bo, and P. Nijkamp. 2011. "Smart Cities in Europe." *Journal of Urban Technology* 18, no. 2: 65–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2011.601117>.
- Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party, & State Council of the People's Republic of China. 2017. "健康中国2030." 规划纲要.
- Chang, V. 2021. "An Ethical Framework for Big Data and Smart Cities." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 165: 120559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120559>.
- Chen, B., S. Marvin, and A. While. 2020. "Containing COVID-19 in China: AI and the Robotic Restructuring of Future Cities." *Dialogues in Human Geography* 10, no. 2: 238–241. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043820620934267>.
- Chen, Y., Z. Yin, and Q. Xie. 2014. "Suggestions to Ameliorate the Inequity in Urban/rural Allocation of Healthcare Resources in China." *International Journal for Equity in Health* 13, no. 1: 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-9276-13-34>.
- Crawford, K., and R. Calo. 2016. "There Is a Blind Spot in AI Research." *Nature* 538, no. 7625: 311–313. <https://doi.org/10.1038/538311a>.
- Creswell, J. W., and V. L. P. Clark. 2017. *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Sage publications.
- Cugurullo, F. 2018. *The Origin of the Smart City Imaginary*. Routledge Companion to Urban Imaginaries.
- Cugurullo, F. 2020. "Urban Artificial Intelligence: From Automation to Autonomy in the Smart City." *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities* 2: 38. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2020.00038>.
- Cugurullo, F. 2021. *Frankenstein Urbanism: Eco, Smart and Autonomous Cities, Artificial Intelligence and the End of the City*. Routledge.
- Cugurullo, F., F. Caprotti, M. Cook, A. Karvonen, P. McGuirk, and S. Marvin. 2023. *Artificial Intelligence and the City: Urbanistic Perspectives on AI*. Taylor & Francis.

- Cugurullo, F., F. Caprotti, M. Cook, A. Karvonen, P. McGuirk, and S. Marvin. 2024. "The Rise of AI Urbanism in Post-smart Cities: A Critical Commentary on Urban Artificial Intelligence." *Urban Studies* 61, no. 6: 1168–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00420980231203386>.
- Cugurullo, F., and Y. Xu. 2024. "When AIs Become Oracles: Generative Artificial Intelligence, Anticipatory Urban Governance, and the Future of Cities." *Policy and Society*: puae025.
- Cuppini, N., S. Barns, F. Bignami, et al. 2025. "Towards an Extended Concept of Citizenship in a Digital Urban Environment." *Nature Cities*: 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44284-025-00236-8>.
- Davenport, T., and R. Kalakota. 2019. "The Potential for Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare." *Future Healthc J* 6, no. 2: 94–98. <https://doi.org/10.7861/futurehosp.6-2-94>.
- Dogan, E., and A. Stupar. 2017. "The Limits of Growth: A Case Study of Three Mega-Projects in Istanbul." *Cities* 60: 281–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2016.09.013>.
- Duan, Y., J. S. Edwards, and Y. K. Dwivedi. 2019. "Artificial Intelligence for Decision Making in the Era of Big Data—Evolution, Challenges and Research Agenda." *International Journal of Information Management* 48: 63–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.01.021>.
- Dúason, S., B. Gunnarsson, and M. H. Svavarsdóttir. 2021. "Patient Handover Between Ambulance Crew and Healthcare Professionals in Icelandic Emergency Departments: A Qualitative Study." *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine* 29, no. 1: 1–11.
- Dwivedi, Y. K., L. Hughes, E. Ismagilova, et al. 2019. "Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Emerging Challenges, Opportunities, and Agenda for Research, Practice and Policy." *International Journal of Information Management* 57: 101994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.08.002>.
- Ekman, A., and C. de Esperanza Picardo. 2020. In *Towards Urban Decoupling? China's Smart City Ambitions at the Time of Covid-19*. European Union Institute for Security Studies: May, 14, 2020.
- Elliott, I. C., J. A. Puppim de Oliveira, and A. M. Wu. 2024. "Public Administration and Development in (Historical) Perspective." *Public Administration and Development* 44, no. 4: 298–314. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.2052>.
- Esteva, A., A. Robicquet, B. Ramsundar, et al. 2019. "A Guide to Deep Learning in Healthcare." *Nature Medicine* 25, no. 1: 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0316-z>.
- Flyvbjerg, B., N. Bruzelius, and W. Rothengatter. 2003. *Megaprojects and Risk: An Anatomy of Ambition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Flyvbjerg, B., & Turner, J. R. (2018). *Do Classics Exist in Megaproject Management?* In (Vol. 36, pp. 334–341): Elsevier.
- Fong, M. W. 2009. "Digital Divide Between Urban and Rural Regions in China." *Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries* 36, no. 1: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2009.tb00253.x>.
- General Office of the State Council. 2018. "国务院办公厅关于促进'互联网+医疗健康'发展的意见." Retrieved from. http://www.gov.cn/zhenqce/content/2018-04/28/content_5286645.htm.
- Geoghegan, S., and F. Cugurullo. 2025. "Beyond Dystopian Smart Cities? Unlocking a Progressive Utopian Future in Smart Urbanism." *Urban Geography*: 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2025.2496508>.
- Gracias, J. S., G. S. Parnell, E. Specking, E. A. Pohl, and R. Buchanan. 2023. "Smart Cities—A Structured Literature Review." *Smart Cities* 6, no. 4: 1719–1743. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities6040080>.
- Graham, S., and S. Marvin. 2002. *Splintering Urbanism: Networked Infrastructures, Technological Mobilities and the Urban Condition*. Routledge.
- Guangdong second provincial general hospital. 2022. "Guangdong Second Provincial General Hospital Profile." <https://www.gd2h.com/yygk/>.
- Guangzhou Development and Reform Commission. 2022. "广州市2022年重点项目计划. Guangzhou."
- Guo, Z., and F. Cugurullo. 2023. "AI Doctors or AI for Doctors?: Augmenting Urban Healthcare Services through Artificial Intelligence." In *Artificial Intelligence and the City*, 307–321. Routledge.
- Hamet, P., and J. Tremblay. 2017. "Artificial Intelligence in Medicine." *Metabolism* 69S: S36–S40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metabol.2017.01.011>.
- Ho, A. 2018. "AI Can Solve China's Doctor Shortage. Here's How." World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/09/ai-can-solve-chinas-doctor-shortage-here-s-how>.
- Hollands, R. G. 2020. "Will the Real Smart City Please Stand up?: Intelligent, Progressive or Entrepreneurial?" In *The Routledge Companion to Smart Cities*, 179–199. Routledge.
- Hu, Y., A. P. Chan, Y. Le, Y. Xu, and M. Shan. 2016. "Developing a Program Organization Performance Index for Delivering Construction Megaprojects in China: Fuzzy Synthetic Evaluation Analysis." *Journal of Management in Engineering* 32, no. 4: 05016007. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)me.1943-5479.0000432](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)me.1943-5479.0000432).
- Huang, E. 2018. "A Chinese Hospital Is Betting Big on Artificial Intelligence to Treat Patients." In *Quartz*.
- Huang, K., W. Luo, W. Zhang, and J. Li. 2021. "Characteristics and Problems of Smart City Development in China." *Smart Cities* 4, no. 4: 1403–1419. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities4040074>.
- Ingwersen, P., and A. E. Serrano-López. 2018. "Smart City Research 1990–2016." *Scientometrics* 117, no. 2: 1205–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2901-9>.
- Jiang, F., Y. Jiang, H. Zhi, et al. 2017. "Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Past, Present and Future." *Stroke and vascular neurology* 2, no. 4: 230–243. <https://doi.org/10.1136/svn-2017-000101>.
- Johnson, A. E., T. J. Pollard, L. Shen, et al. 2016. "MIMIC-III, a Freely Accessible Critical Care Database." *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.35>.
- Kamruzzaman, M. 2021. "New Opportunities, Challenges, and Applications of Edge-AI for Connected Healthcare in Smart Cities." In *2021 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*.
- Karvonen, A., F. Cugurullo, and F. Caprotti. 2018. In *Inside Smart Cities: Place, Politics and Urban Innovation*. 1st. Routledge. https://tcdlibrary.lids.org.uk/vdc_100066351214.0x000001.
- Kassens-Noor, E., K. Darcy, A. I. Cojocar, et al. 2022. "Proposing the Foundations of scaInce by Exploring the Future of Artificially Intelligent, Sustainable, and Resilient Megaprojects." *Journal of Mega Infrastructure & Sustainable Development* 2, no. sup1: 5–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24724718.2022.2131098>.
- Kassens-Noor, E., and A. Hintze. 2020. "Cities of the Future? the Potential Impact of Artificial Intelligence." *AI* 1, no. 2: 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ai1020012>.
- Kitchin, R. 2015. "Making Sense of Smart Cities: Addressing Present Shortcomings." *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society* 8, no. 1: 131–136. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsu027>.
- Kitchin, R. 2016. "The Ethics of Smart Cities and Urban Science." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical & Engineering Sciences* 374, no. 2083: 20160115. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0115>.
- Kitchin, R., T. P. Lauriault, and G. McArdle. 2017. "Data and the City." In *Data and the City*, 1–13. Routledge.
- Kostkova, P., H. Brewer, S. De Lusignan, et al. 2016. "Who Owns the Data? Open Data for Healthcare." *Frontiers in Public Health* 4: 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2016.00007>.
- Li, C., J. Wang, S. Wang, and Y. Zhang. 2023. "A Review of IoT Applications in Healthcare." *Neurocomputing*: 127017.

- Li, G., W. Lian, H. Qu, Z. Li, Q. Zhou, and J. Tian. 2021. "Improving Patient Care through the Development of a 5G-Powered Smart Hospital." *Nature Medicine* 27, no. 6: 936–937. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01376-9>.
- Li, X., H. M. Krumholz, W. Yip, et al. 2020. "Quality of Primary Health Care in China: Challenges and Recommendations." *Lancet* 395, no. 10239: 1802–1812. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30122-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30122-7).
- Liang, H., B. Y. Tsui, H. Ni, et al. 2019. "Evaluation and Accurate Diagnoses of Pediatric Diseases Using Artificial Intelligence." *Nature Medicine* 25, no. 3: 433–438. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0335-9>.
- Luque-Ayala, A., and S. Marvin. 2015. "Developing a Critical Understanding of Smart Urbanism?" *Urban Studies* 52, no. 12: 2105–2116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098015577319>.
- Lv, Q., Y. Jiang, J. Qi, et al. 2019. "Using Mobile Apps for Health Management: A New Health Care Mode in China." *JMIR mHealth and uHealth* 7, no. 6: e10299. <https://doi.org/10.2196/10299>.
- Macrorie, R., S. Marvin, and A. While. 2019. "Robotics and Automation in the City: A Research Agenda." *Urban Geography* 42, no. 2: 197–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2019.1698868>.
- Marvin, S., A. While, B. Chen, and M. Kovacic. 2022. "Urban AI in China: Social Control or Hyper-Capitalist Development in the Post-Smart City?" *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities* 155. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2022.1030318>.
- Mayer-Schönberger, V., and K. Cukier. 2013. *Big Data: A Revolution that Will Transform How We Live, Work, and Think*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- McDonough, C. C. 2016. "The Effect of Ageism on the Digital Divide Among Older Adults." *J. Gerontol. Geriatr. Med* 2, no. 8: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.24966/ggm-8662/100008>.
- Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development. 2020. "China Urban Construction Statistical Yearbook."
- Morley, J., C. C. Machado, C. Burr, et al. 2020. "The Ethics of AI in Health Care: A Mapping Review." *Social Science & Medicine* 260: 113172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113172>.
- Moulaei, K., A. Yadegari, M. Baharestani, S. Farzanbakhsh, B. Sabet, and M. R. Afrash. 2024. "Generative Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: A Scoping Review on Benefits, Challenges and Applications." *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 188: 105474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2024.105474>.
- Mousa, M., D. Althalathini, and V. Puhakka. 2025. "When Grand Societal Challenges Stimulate the Creation of Public Value: A Study of Nurses in a Non-Western Public Healthcare Sector." *Public Administration and Development* 45, no. 2: 146–158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.2093>.
- Nam, T., and T. A. Pardo. 2011. "Conceptualizing Smart City With Dimensions of Technology, People, and Institutions." In *Proceedings of the 12th Annual International Digital Government Research Conference: Digital Government Innovation in Challenging Times*.
- National Health Commission. 2017. "'十三五' 全国人口健康信息化发展规划." Retrieved from. <http://www.nhc.gov.cn/guihuaxxs/s10741/201702/ef9ba6f82ef46a49c333de32275074f.shtml>.
- National Health Commission. 2020. "国家卫生健康委办公厅关于进一步完善预约诊疗制度加强智慧医院建设的通知." Retrieved from. <http://www.nhc.gov.cn/yzygj/s3594q/202005/b2adae99376d4af0834fd8d43c5d4b4f.shtml>.
- Palmini, O., and F. Cugurullo. 2023. "Charting AI Urbanism: Conceptual Sources and Spatial Implications of Urban Artificial Intelligence." *Discover Artificial Intelligence* 3, no. 1: 15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44163-023-00060-w>.
- Pencheva, I., M. Esteve, and S. J. Mikhaylov. 2018. "Big Data and AI – A Transformational Shift for Government: So, what Next for Research?" *Public Policy and Administration* 35, no. 1: 24–44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076718780537>.
- Raghupathi, W., and V. Raghupathi. 2014. "Big Data Analytics in Healthcare: Promise and Potential." *Health Information Science and Systems* 2: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2047-2501-2-3>.
- Rathi, V. K., N. K. Rajput, S. Mishra, et al. 2021. "An Edge AI-Enabled IoT Healthcare Monitoring System for Smart Cities." *Computers & Electrical Engineering* 96: 107524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107524>.
- Reddy, S., J. Fox, and M. P. Purohit. 2019. "Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Healthcare Delivery." *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* 112, no. 1: 22–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076818815510>.
- Revyakin, S. A. 2022. "Personal Privacy VS. Public Safety: A Hybrid Model of the Use of Smart City Solutions in Fighting the COVID-19 Pandemic in Moscow." *Public Administration and Development* 42, no. 5: 281–292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1997>.
- Seawright, J., and J. Gerring. 2008. "Case Selection Techniques in Case Study Research: A Menu of Qualitative and Quantitative Options." *Political Research Quarterly* 61, no. 2: 294–308. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1065912907313077>.
- Shah, R., and A. Chircu. 2018. "IOT and Ai in Healthcare: A Systematic Literature Review." *Issues in Information Systems* 19, no. 3.
- Shibata, T., and K. Wada. 2011. "Robot Therapy: A New Approach for Mental Healthcare of the Elderly—A Mini-Review." *Gerontology* 57, no. 4: 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000319015>.
- Shilian, H., Jing, W., Cui, C., & Xinchun, W. (2020). *Analysis of Epidemiological Trends in Chronic Diseases of Chinese Residents*. In (Vol. 3, pp. 226–233): Wiley Online Library.
- Singh, N., M. Jain, M. M. Kamal, R. Bodhi, and B. Gupta. 2024. "Technological Paradoxes and Artificial Intelligence Implementation in Healthcare. An Application of Paradox Theory." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 198: 122967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122967>.
- Sun, S., and Z. Wang. 2021. 多地重大项目集中开工 稳投资加力冲刺. 经济参考报. http://www.news.cn/fortune/2021-11/08/c_1128041619.htm.
- Sun, T. Q., and R. Medaglia. 2019. "Mapping the Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in the Public Sector: Evidence From Public Healthcare." *Government Information Quarterly* 36, no. 2: 368–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2018.09.008>.
- Tagde, P., S. Tagde, T. Bhattacharya, et al. 2021. "Blockchain and Artificial Intelligence Technology in e-Health." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 28, no. 38: 52810–52831. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16223-0>.
- Tencent. 2021. "Tencent Holdings Limited 2021 Annual Report." <https://static.www.tencent.com/uploads/2022/04/07/7c31a327fb1c068906b70ba7ebede899.PDF>.
- Topol, E. J. 2019. "High-performance Medicine: The Convergence of Human and Artificial Intelligence." *Nature Medicine* 25, no. 1: 44–56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0300-7>.
- Trajkovski, G. 2024. "Bridging the Public administration-AI Divide: A Skills Perspective." *Public Administration and Development* 44, no. 5: 412–426. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.2061>.
- Trencher, G. 2019. "Towards the Smart City 2.0: Empirical Evidence of Using Smartness as a Tool for Tackling Social Challenges." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 142: 117–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.07.033>.
- Van Kleek, M., W. Seymour, M. Veale, R. Binns, and N. Shadbolt. 2018. "The Need for Sensemaking in Networked Privacy and Algorithmic Responsibility." *Sensemaking in a Senseless World: Workshop at ACM CHI'18, 22 April 2018, Montréal, Canada*.

- Van Marrewijk, A., S. R. Clegg, T. S. Pitsis, and M. Veenswijk. 2008. "Managing Public-Private Megaprojects: Paradoxes, Complexity, and Project Design." *International Journal of Project Management* 26, no. 6: 591-600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2007.09.007>.
- Vinuesa, R., H. Azizpour, I. Leite, et al. 2020. "The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals." *Nature Communications* 11, no. 1: 233. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14108-y>.
- Wang, Z., Y. Chen, T. Pan, X. Liu, and H. Hu. 2019. "The Comparison of Healthcare Utilization Inequity Between URRBMI and NCMS in Rural China." *International Journal for Equity in Health* 18, no. 1: 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-019-0987-1>.
- Wei, J. 2018. "Research Progress and Application of Computer Artificial Intelligence Technology." In *MATEC Web of Conferences*.
- Wenfang, L. 2018. "Guangzhou Hospital Opens AI Lab to Create E-Hospital. China Daily." <https://global.chinadaily.com.cn/a/201805/10/WS5af4377fa3105cdcf651d320.html>.
- While, A. H., S. Marvin, and M. Kovacic. 2020. "Urban Robotic experimentation: San Francisco, Tokyo and Dubai." *Urban Studies* 58, no. 4: 769-786. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098020917790>.
- Wisskirchen, G., B. T. Biacabe, U. Bormann, et al. 2017. *Artificial Intelligence and Robotics and Their Impact on the Workplace, 2012-2017*. IBA Global Employment Institute.
- Wu, W., D. Zhu, W. Liu, and C.-H. Wu. 2022. "Empirical Research on Smart City Construction and Public Health under Information and Communications Technology." *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences* 80: 100994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2020.100994>.
- Xiang, D., and W. Cai. 2021. "Privacy Protection and Secondary Use of Health Data: Strategies and Methods." *BioMed Research International* 2021, no. 1: 6967166. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6967166>.
- Xu, Y., F. Cugurullo, H. Zhang, A. Gaio, and W. Zhang. 2024. "The Emergence of Artificial Intelligence in Anticipatory Urban Governance: Multi-Scalar Evidence of China's Transition to City Brains." *Journal of Urban Technology*: 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2023.2292823>.
- Yigitcanlar, T., and F. Cugurullo. 2020. "The Sustainability of Artificial Intelligence: An Urbanistic Viewpoint From the Lens of Smart and Sustainable Cities." *Sustainability* 12, no. 20: 8548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208548>.
- Yigitcanlar, T., K. Desouza, L. Butler, and F. Roozkhosh. 2020. "Contributions and Risks of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Building Smarter Cities: Insights From a Systematic Review of the Literature." *Energies* 13, no. 6: 1473. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13061473>.
- Yigitcanlar, T., S. Senadheera, R. Marasinghe, et al. 2024. "Artificial Intelligence and the Local Government: A Five-Decade Scientometric Analysis on the Evolution, State-Of-The-Art, and Emerging Trends." *Cities* 152: 105151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105151>.
- Yin, R. K. 2014. *Case Study Research: Design and Methods (Applied Social Research Methods)*. Sage publications.
- Yuan, H., W. Du, Z. Wang, and X. Song. 2021. "Megaproject Management Research: The Status Quo and Future Directions." *Buildings* 11, no. 12: 567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11120567>.
- Zheng, X., and C. Rodriguez-Monroy. 2015. "The Development of Intelligent Healthcare in China." *Telemedicine Journal and e-Health* 21, no. 5: 443-448. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2014.0102>.
- Zweig, D. 2006. "Competing for Talent: China's Strategies to Reverse the Brain Drain." *Int'l Lab. Rev.* 145, no. 1-2: 65-90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1564-913x.2006.tb00010.x>.
- 何雪华. 2021. "酷!广东首次启用检测样本无人机配送." *Guangzhou Daily*. <https://m.huanqiu.com/article/43LbKOHBaQs>.
- 宫芳芳, 孙喜琢, 林君, and 顾晓东. 2013. "我国智慧医疗建设初探." *现代医院管理*, no. 2: 2.
- 朱力, and 袁迎春. 2014. "现阶段我国医患矛盾的类型、特征与对策." *社会科学研究*, no. 6: 8.
- 游世梅. 2015. "智慧医疗的现状与发展趋势." *中华医学会医学工程学会第十五次全国学术年会论文汇编*
- 王圣媛. 2017. "发展基于人工智能的智能医药监管系统——访中国工程院院士李兰娟." *中国战略新兴产业* 4, no. 13.
- 罗平章, and 张仕杰. 2021. "国内首家全场景智能医院落地广东 患者将有这些新体验." *China Central Television*. https://content-static.cctv.cn/cctv.com/snow-book/index.html?toc_style_id=feeds_default&share_to=copy_url&item_id=12832131776590666029&track_id=65B26167-752A-4B97-9732-1095D3198661_676597863541.
- 董华, and 刘太强. 2014. "我国智慧医疗发展现状及问题分析." *中小企业管理与科技*.
- 陈敏. 2018. "'互联网+医疗健康':打造智慧医疗服务新模式." *中国党政干部论坛*.
- 项高悦, 曾智, and 沈永健. 2016. "我国智慧医疗建设的现状及发展趋势探究." *中国全科医学*.